

Can green hydrogen support fossil fuel workers? Examining workforce transition pathways in oil and gas communities

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1. Introduction

Efforts to mitigate ongoing and future impacts of climate change will require a rapid decarbonization of the energy sector and a large-scale transition away from current fossil fuel consumption. While this transition is necessary, it risks exacerbating existing inequities created by our energy system and potentially introduces new inequities as communities and workers previously supported by fossil fuel industries are left behind [1, 2]. Thus, critical examination of these impacts is necessary to develop policies and other mechanisms to facilitate a just energy transition. Historically, the concept of the just transition has been tied to labor movements, as workers and communities previously supported by declining industries attempt to move into new sectors [3]. While the concept has expanded in scope to include and emphasize energy and environmental justice, governance, and socio-technical impacts, labor and workforce impacts remain a key component of the just transition [4, 5, 6]. Workers in fossil fuel industries, in particular, have received significant attention as the rise of new green industries, along with energy and environmental regulations, places them and their communities at significant risk of sustained economic impacts including unemployment and lost wages [7, 8]. Proactive planning and an understanding of local economic impacts are critical to ensuring a just transition and identifying pathways to transition fossil fuel workers into new jobs created by the energy transition [9, 10].

Existing literature has demonstrated that the growth of new renewable energy technologies could generate enough jobs to support workers in fossil fuel sectors [5, 11, 12]. However, while there is likely to be a net increase in available jobs, assessments tend to be performed at the national or state level and rarely reflect the regional disparities [13]. Studies developing regional assessments have found that new clean energy jobs are unlikely to be located in the same regions as existing fossil fuel employment, and this location gap is a major barrier to transitioning workers to this new sector [14, 15]. Moreover, attempts to close this gap by shifting renewable capacity closer to existing workers can result in significant cost increases [16]. Impacts are also likely to vary across different industries and occupations. Coal workers, for example, are expected to be more severely impacted by job losses [17], and extraction workers (e.g., oil rig operators, fracking technicians, etc.) as a group are the most vulnerable of those employed by fossil fuel companies.

Beyond identifying these distributional gaps, additional efforts are needed to fully understand the differences in both skill requirements and job quality between existing and emerging energy jobs [15]. While some studies have shown that green jobs tend to have skill requirements more similar to those of fossil fuel jobs than those of other sectors [14], there are persistent gaps in their current skill profiles, particularly in non-technical skills, that could limit their transferability [18]. Furthermore, policymakers and researchers tend to focus on comparing the skills of fossil fuel workers to exclusively green jobs. However, the energy transition will require a wide range of occupations, such as manufacturing jobs, that can support diverse skill profiles. This suggests that there is an additional need to understand where fossil fuel workers fit into this landscape beyond

jobs directly related to green energy technologies [19]. The rate at which fossil fuel workers transition to green jobs is expected to increase as new green jobs become available, but certain groups, particularly those without a college education or older workers, are unlikely to transition [20].

In addition to understanding the feasibility of transitioning to new sectors, it is also critical to understand the differences in overall job quality to ensure fossil fuel workers are well-supported in new fields. Definitions of job quality vary considerably, can encompass both economic and non-economic elements of a job, and often depend on individual workers' perceptions and values [21, 22, 23]. One persistent aspect of job quality is annual wages, as workers generally want to ensure their work is well compensated and would be hesitant to transition to a new industry if they were to experience a wage loss. While many areas of green jobs are likely to experience wage increases over time, this growth is not distributed uniformly across states or sectors [5]. Coal workers, for example, are expected to experience significant earnings losses that could persist for years after transitioning to a new industry [24].

Given the potential gaps between current fossil fuel jobs and emerging green jobs, other emerging technologies may be more closely aligned to the needs of current fossil fuel workers and better suited to supporting them in an energy transition. Hydrogen, in particular, has emerged as an alternative energy carrier due to its potential to decarbonize hard-to-electrify sectors like industrial processes and heavy-duty transportation. Due to the nascent nature of this sector, current understanding of the workforce impacts of hydrogen production is limited. Early case studies demonstrate the potential for hydrogen production and end-use demand to generate a significant number of jobs [25, 26]. The hydrogen hubs currently being developed in the US, for example, can potentially create tens of thousands of jobs during construction and operation [27]. While these early estimates are promising, the distribution of new jobs across regions in a large-scale hydrogen economy remains underexplored, and it is unclear to what extent hydrogen jobs could close or exacerbate the distributional gap between fossil fuel and renewable jobs. Moreover, as governments and stakeholders attempt to develop this emerging workforce, there is a need to understand what skill profiles to prioritize and how to best support workers coming from other sectors, like the fossil fuel industry with sufficient education and training opportunities [28, 29, 30, 31].

Quantifying and understanding the potential impacts of new hydrogen technologies are critical to avoiding exacerbating existing inequities and identifying pathways to most effectively leverage these new technologies [32]. To contribute to these efforts, this study seeks to quantify the extent to which emerging hydrogen production technologies, specifically electrolytic hydrogen (i.e., hydrogen produced from water using renewable electricity), can serve to reduce the location, skill, and quality gaps between current fossil fuel workers and future jobs created by the energy transition. Given the need for more granular assessments of job distributions [33], we develop a case study of the Texas Interconnection, which, in the US, has the largest utility-scale wind and solar projects, is the current largest producer of hydrogen, and has one of the largest fossil fuel workforces [34, 35, 36]. We use a capacity expansion model of the power sector and hydrogen supply chain to quantify the amount of new generation capacity associated with green hydrogen

production across different policy and demand scenarios. We then pair the capacity expansion model with a set of economic input-output models to quantify the number of jobs created by the deployment of this new capacity in each scenario, thereby assessing the distribution of jobs across the state. The breakdown of new renewable energy and hydrogen jobs by occupation is then combined with existing data on skill and knowledge requirements, training needs, and wages to understand how the skill gap and wage gaps between oil and gas and hydrogen jobs compare to renewable energy occupations. This analysis offers critical insights into an emerging industry that can inform the development of effective policies and programs. It aims to support the development of a skilled hydrogen workforce and help understand how these jobs can be leveraged to support oil and gas workers and facilitate a just transition.

2. Methods

To understand the potential workforce development impacts of the emerging hydrogen supply chain, this study integrates capacity expansion modeling with established economic input-output models as well as occupational databases, as summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic of the methodologies used in this analysis

2.1 Electric Grid-Hydrogen Sector Coupling Model

First, we develop a capacity expansion model of the Texas Interconnection to model investment decisions for both the power sector and the hydrogen supply chain. For this model, we use SWITCH [37], an open-source capacity expansion model that has been used to guide long-term grid planning decisions in regions and countries all over the world [38, 39, 40, 41]. We use SWITCH-ERCOT, as developed in Potts and Castellanos [42, 43], which consists of a nine-zone

representation of the Texas Interconnection modeled in five-year investment periods from 2025 to 2050 (Supplemental Figure S1). Additional information on the model formulation is available in the supplemental materials. For each investment period, we model one full representative year in four-hour time steps. Projected cost data for candidate technologies in the power sector are derived from the 2024 Annual Technology Baseline from the National Laboratory of the Rockies (NLR), and existing generation infrastructure is based on the EIA Form 860 [44, 45]. Candidate technologies for the power sector include utility-scale solar, onshore wind, natural gas, coal, nuclear, bioenergy, geothermal, and battery storage. In addition to the power sector, we include a representation of the hydrogen supply chain. Hydrogen production options include steam methane reformation (with and without carbon capture), as well as proton exchange membrane electrolyzers. Since SWITCH is designed for bulk representations of the transmission system, we only consider grid-connected electrolyzers in this analysis. However, to mitigate the potential emissions impacts of grid-connected electrolyzers and to be consistent with federal guidelines, we also impose geographical matching, hourly matching, and additionality constraints on electrolyzers [46, 47]. These constraints ensure that all hydrogen production is matched by a proportional amount of generation from new wind and solar technologies located in the same region as the electrolyzer.

We use six scenarios to quantify the range of potential economic impacts of hydrogen given uncertain demand and policy outcomes (Table 1). We model two different demand projections: One that captures only current hydrogen demand and assumes no future growth, and another that represents the maximum potential demand for hydrogen for both industrial processes and transportation, based on projected potential for these end-use sectors in Texas [36]. Then, given uncertainty about future energy and carbon policies, we model each demand profile with three different policy assumptions: (i) A sub-scenario where no policies are modeled (NP-C and NP-IT in Table 1); (ii) one where the clean energy and hydrogen tax credits from the Inflation Reduction Act are extended through 2050 (IRA-C and IRA-IT); and (iii) a net-zero scenario, where carbon emissions are forced to be zero by 2050 (NZ-C and NZ-IT) [48].

Table 1. Summary of scenario names and their corresponding hydrogen demand and policies.

Scenario Name	Policy	Hydrogen Demand
NP-C	No Policy	Current
NP-IT	No Policy	Industrial + Transportation
IRA-C	IRA	Current
IRA-IT	IRA	Industrial + Transportation
NZ-C	Net-Zero	Current
NZ-IT	Net-Zero	Industrial + Transportation

2.2 Workforce Development Impacts

Once results from SWITCH-ERCOT are obtained, we quantify the installed capacity for hydrogen electrolyzers and the amount of new renewable energy capacity attributable to the buildout of the hydrogen supply chain. This is determined by comparing the installed capacity of wind and solar

in each scenario with an equivalent scenario that excludes hydrogen demand and computing the difference. Once these capacities are identified, we use a series of economic input-output (IO) models to quantify the number of jobs created over the time horizon of the model. In this context, new jobs can be broken down into distinct classifications depending on the economic activity that creates them. Direct jobs include construction jobs and any on-site labor associated with the new project. Indirect jobs are typically jobs upstream in the supply chain generated from the economic activity and purchases required to support the development and operation of the new project. Lastly, induced jobs are tertiary impacts generated by spending and economic activity of employees spending their wages. While it is common to estimate employment impacts of energy infrastructure using employment factors (EFs; jobs per MW of installed capacity), such parameters often only reflect direct employment impacts, whereas the interactions across industries reflected in IO models allows for estimates of indirect job impacts as well. Moreover, the use of IO models allows us to better reflect variations in regional employment impacts across different industries and technologies [49].

To quantify jobs associated with wind and solar, we use the Jobs and Economic Development Impact models (JEDI) developed by NLR, which have been specifically designed for onshore wind and utility-scale solar installations [50, 51]. Each model quantifies the interactions and interdependencies across aggregated sets of industries given a set of project cost assumptions and projected installed capacity. We define custom regions in each JEDI model that correspond to the nine load zones in this study by providing region-specific economic multipliers for employment, earnings, industry output, value added, and personal consumption expenditures obtained from IMPLAN [52]. Additionally, we assume that local content, or the fraction of demand that can be met by local industries and supply chains, for all components to be 100% for both wind and solar. While this is not reflective of current economic activity, it provides an upper bound for the potential local impacts of new renewable energy infrastructure if regional and local supply chains are developed. Lastly, project cost data is updated to reflect more recent cost estimates wherever applicable to account for more recent economic data, as estimated by NLR's Annual Technology Baseline [44].

Given the limited availability of open-source IO models for hydrogen infrastructure, this study develops a custom model of the economic impacts of hydrogen electrolyzers in IMPLAN. First, to simplify the economic analysis, we aggregate the 528 industries in IMPLAN into 22 industries based on existing literature and economic data on electrolyzers and the industries expected to be most relevant to their construction and operation (Supplemental Table S1). Once the aggregation is defined, we split the capital expenditures for electrolyzers across their individual components (e.g., power supply, water circulation, coated catalyst membrane) [53]. Note that we assume present-day electrolyzers costs for this stage of the analysis and do not account for potential future cost reductions [54]. Then, the cost of the individual components is split between several of the 22 aggregated industries based on existing literature on these different components and their manufacturing requirements [55, 56]. To reflect operational impacts of electrolyzers, we perform a similar disaggregation for the fixed operation & maintenance costs, which we assume to be 3% of capital costs. These industry-level impacts are then used as inputs into the regional IMPLAN models for each load zone to quantify the jobs created by new electrolyzer capacity.

Since the outputs of SWITCH only determine the total amount of capacity that is installed in a region and not individual projects, we need to account for economies of scale. To do this, we model the workforce development impacts of a single wind, solar, or electrolyzer project whose nameplate capacity is equal to the average capacity of all existing capacity in the load zone to reflect typical project sizes. If there is no existing wind or solar capacity in a load zone, the state average is used instead (189 MW and 109 MW respectively). Given the lack of project data for electrolyzers, we assume a project size of 300 MW. The employment impacts for a single project are then scaled up based on the total installed capacity in SWITCH to get the total employment impact in each load zone. The results of both the JEDI and IMPLAN models reveal the employment impacts of new renewable energy and hydrogen infrastructure in each load zone for each scenario. Employment impacts include a combination of direct jobs, indirect jobs, and induced jobs. To address observations that only a small fraction of fossil fuel workers are likely to transition to jobs in renewable energy [14], which would correspond to direct employments, we include indirect jobs in other industries (e.g., manufacturing) that may have some skill overlap to capture a range of potential career pathways that become available as a result of hydrogen production. Induced jobs are not considered in this analysis as their tertiary impacts are difficult to quantify, highly sensitive to modeling assumption and tend to be in industries that are dissimilar to existing fossil fuel occupations. The results of the IO models are compared to jobs data for existing fossil fuel industries in Texas. County-level employment data for ten industries from the North American Industry Classification System (NAICS) related to the oil and gas sector are obtained from the Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS) and aggregated to match the geographical regions used in SWITCH, allowing for a direct comparison with the employment results from JEDI and IMPLAN [57]. The selected industries predominantly focus on oil and gas extraction, pipeline operations, and power plant operations (Supplemental Table S2).

2.3 Occupational Data Analysis

To assess the skill requirements of existing oil and gas jobs and prospective green energy jobs, we utilize occupational data from the Occupational Information Network (O*NET) database [58]. The O*NET database provides a comprehensive description of the skills, knowledge requirements, and tasks associated with over 900 occupations in the US and has been leveraged in prior studies to compare skill requirements across different energy sector jobs [5, 14, 18, 59]. For this study, we focus on three main aspects of each occupation – (i) skill requirements, (ii) knowledge requirements, and (iii) daily work activities – to better understand the feasibility of transitioning from oil and gas occupations to those associated with renewables and hydrogen. For each of these datasets, workers in an occupation, as defined by the Standard Occupational Classification (SOC) taxonomy, estimate both the importance and the level of complexity using ratings of 1–5 and 0–7, respectively, where higher values indicate greater importance or higher complexity. Using a subset of the occupations described above, we first perform a pairwise comparison of each oil and gas occupation with each renewable occupation and repeat this for each hydrogen occupation. Multiple similarity metrics have been used in studies of the skills gap for emerging green jobs [59]. For this analysis, we use the real-valued Jaccard similarity metric described in Lim et al. [14]. Thus, for any two occupations, we can compare the normalized importance or level of complexity of skills or activities using a single metric, as shown in Equation 1.

$$Jaccard\ Similarity_{i,j} = \frac{\sum_{s \in Skills} \min(s_i, s_j)}{\sum_{s \in Skills} \max(s_i, s_j)} \quad (1)$$

where a similarity value of 1 indicates that the two occupations (i, j) have identical skill requirements. To reflect existing oil and gas occupations, we identify a subset of occupations within the ten NAICS fossil fuel industries previously identified that are directly tied to oil and gas. We emphasize extraction workers in this subset, given their vulnerability to the energy transition, but also include other related occupations (Supplemental Table S3). Renewable occupations are identified using existing lists of SOC classifications that are associated with green jobs [60]. We filter this category to emphasize jobs associated with wind and solar technologies specifically, and then include associated manufacturing jobs identified using the occupation multipliers from IMPLAN (Supplemental Table S4). Hydrogen occupations are identified using data from the IMPLAN model and focus primarily on jobs associated with gas production and processing, as well as related manufacturing jobs (Supplemental Table S5).

In addition, we also consider both the education and training data, and wage data for each occupation. O*NET education and training data use distinct classifications for different levels of education (e.g., High school diploma, associate's degree) and report data as percentages of all jobs for that specific occupation. This data is combined with estimates of new job openings per occupation from each of our IO models to get a distribution of requirements for each job classification. Similarly, we incorporate 2023 annual mean wage data for each occupation from the BLS, and scale wage data based on new employment opportunities to estimate wage differences across sectors [61]. Here, we only consider present-day wages and do not make any projections or estimates of future earnings across different sectors.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 2a shows the installed capacity in 2050 for hydrogen electrolyzers, wind, and solar in ERCOT across a series of policy and demand scenarios. The introduction of hydrogen electrolyzers can result in anywhere from 39.8 to 297.2 GW of new cumulative capacity, depending on the scenario. Pairing a net-zero CO₂ constraint with both industrial and transportation demand results in installed capacity more than doubling compared to the next-highest scenario. Despite electrolyzer capacity only ranging from 8.5 to 43.1 GW, they require anywhere from 2.6 to 5.9 times their rated capacity in new renewable capacity to operate consistently. In net-zero scenarios, this new capacity is predominantly solar, but cases with less strict policies like extended tax credits from the IRA tend to favor wind, so the exact distribution of capacity and jobs across technologies is sensitive to policy implementations.

Figure 2. (a) Cumulative installed capacity of hydrogen electrolyzers, wind, and solar in 2050. The installed capacity for wind and solar only represents the new renewable capacity in ERCOT whose installation is attributed to the electricity demand of new electrolyzers. (b) Total temporary direct and indirect job-years during the construction period for new wind, solar, and electrolyzers. (c) Number of direct and indirect jobs created by the operation and maintenance of wind, solar, and electrolyzers.

Figure 2b shows the total number of job-years created during the construction periods (2025–2050) for each technology. Total employment opportunity generated by construction ranges from 167,000 to 978,000 job-years, with a significant majority of these new jobs being created by solar installations in all scenarios. Installation of the new power capacity (Fig. 2a) can significantly increase jobs in a region, but opportunities created by construction are temporary and will only be available for several years at most depending on construction and installation time. While these jobs could be sustained for longer periods if renewable and electrolyzer capacity is installed gradually over the next 25 years, our results indicate that there are several short periods of rapid expansion with periods of much slower infrastructure growth in between. In particular, there is significant capacity expansion over the first 5–10 years due to a combination of existing tax credits and projected doubling of electricity demand by 2033, and again in 2050, when overnight capital costs for these technologies are at their lowest. Given this, local construction-related jobs would not be well-suited to temporarily supporting oil and gas communities, as short-term growth is unlikely to coincide with significant retirements of oil and gas assets, and would instead rely on labor brought in from other sectors or other parts of the country.

The new jobs created as a result of the operation and maintenance of new energy infrastructure are shown in Fig. 2c. Depending on the scenario, total operation jobs range from 9.2K to about 66K new jobs, with the NZ-IT scenario having more than double the number of jobs compared to the next highest scenario (32.1K jobs in the IRA-IT scenario). This equates to anywhere from 5.1% to 36.6% of the existing oil and gas employees considered in this analysis. While emerging hydrogen production cannot support most oil and gas workers, it can provide a significant supplement to other workforce opportunities in the energy transition, provided there is sufficient policy support to drive both hydrogen production and demand. As with construction jobs, operational jobs are dominated by those associated with new solar capacity. This is also reflected in the considerably higher EFs for solar installation and operations (Table 2). The EFs for wind and solar are relatively

low, particularly for solar, but are consistent with other reported values in literature [16, 62]. Electrolyzers have construction EFs on par with solar installations, but they have lower operational EFs that are comparable to new wind capacity. This, combined with the comparatively low installed capacity of electrolyzers, suggests that the workforce contributions from electrolyzers will largely come from the new wind and solar capacity required to power them, rather than from hydrogen production itself. These EFs for electrolyzers are consistent with other input-output models of electrolyzers, though some estimates suggest that EFs can be significantly higher than the values reported here [26, 63]. Additionally, these EFs only consider direct jobs. When indirect jobs are included, the EFs for electrolyzers are 61–64% higher compared to wind, suggesting greater upstream supply chain impacts associated with electrolyzers relative to other technologies.

Table 2. Employment factor ranges for each technology based on the results of their corresponding input-output models for each scenario.

Job Type	Employment Factor (EF)	Solar	Wind	Electrolyzer
Direct	Installation Employment Factor (job-year/MW)	2.90–7.35	0.25–0.33	3.70–3.94
	Operation Employment Factor (job/MW)	0.20–0.43	0.11–0.13	0.10–0.12
Direct + Indirect	Installation Employment Factor (job-year/MW)	3.52–8.74	0.88–0.98	5.44–5.59
	Operation Employment Factor (job/MW)	0.23–0.53	0.13–0.14	0.21–0.23

Figure 3 shows the distribution of jobs across each load zone for each scenario. Here, we consider all direct and indirect jobs that are expected to persist over the lifetime of this new capacity. New energy capacity associated with hydrogen production tends to be concentrated in a few specific regions and is consistent across demand and policy scenarios. In particular, regions in the Permian Basin and the Texas panhandle (i.e., “North”, “West”, and “Panhandle” in Fig. 3b) tend to have the greatest number of new jobs. For each of these regions, the number of jobs generated by wind, solar, and electrolyzer operations is sufficient to offset potential job losses for oil and gas workers in at least some scenarios in which this infrastructure is incentivized. However, these regions also have comparatively low oil and gas employment relative to other parts of the state. In particular, the Gulf Coast (i.e., “Coast”) and the western regions of the Permian (i.e., “Far West”) have the greatest number of oil and gas employees by a significant margin. Even in the most optimistic scenario, our results indicate that new jobs in these regions can support 4.6% and 1.9% of oil and gas workers in the Coast and Far West regions, respectively. This suggests that, much like renewable generation, hydrogen production creates a location gap where the jobs generated by electrolyzer operation, as well as associated renewable energy projects, are not accessible to current workers without relocation. In fact, in some cases, new hydrogen capacity can exacerbate the locational gap. Although we only consider capacity gains in this analysis, the introduction of electrolyzers in the region could shift new renewable energy installations away from other parts of

the state to the region where the electrolyzers are being built. This can further concentrate energy infrastructure in specific regions of the state, which, as shown here, are unlikely to be aligned with the locations of current oil and gas workers.

Figure 3. (a) New direct and indirect jobs created during the lifetime of new wind, solar, and electrolyzer capacity in each load zone and scenario, compared to the existing oil and gas jobs

currently in that load zone. (b) Map showing the distribution of new renewables and hydrogen jobs in the NZ-IT scenario across each load zone. The color of each load zone indicates the number of existing oil and gas jobs in that region.

The results of this analysis indicate that expected renewable (VRE) and hydrogen (H₂) occupations, as well as associated manufacturing jobs, are more similar to oil and gas (OG) jobs than to occupations in other sectors. Figures 4a–4c show the probability distribution functions for the pairwise similarity metrics calculated for each combination of OG and VRE jobs, and OG and H₂ jobs. For reference, we present a distribution of the similarity metrics for OG occupations relative to all other SOC occupations. We also perform a simple two-sample *t*-test to determine if the differences in the means are statistically significant. On average, OG occupations exhibit a skill similarity of 0.728 with VRE jobs and 0.732 with H₂ jobs. These average similarities are 8–8.6% percent higher than the average similarity of 0.674 to the full set of SOC occupations. When compared to this distribution, the OG–VRE and OG–H₂ occupation similarities have *p*-values < 0.0001, indicating a statistically significant difference in the means. The distributions of skill similarities for OG–VRE and OG–H₂ occupations overlaps considerably and has a *p*-value > 0.1, indicating no statistically significant difference between their means. Similar patterns emerge when we compute pairwise similarity metrics between knowledge requirements and daily work activities. For knowledge requirements, OG occupations have a similarity score of 0.562 relative to all occupations, but scores of 0.642 and 0.638 when compared to VRE and H₂ occupations, respectively. Work activities exhibited the highest overall similarity with OG occupations, with average scores of 0.715 across all occupations, 0.765 for VRE occupations, and 0.763 for H₂ occupations.

Figure 4: Probability distribution functions of the Jaccard similarity metrics for every pairwise combination of oil and gas occupations with VRE occupations, H₂ occupations, and all other occupations for (a) skill requirements, (b) knowledge requirements, and (c) typical work activities.

A two-sample *t*-test is performed between each distribution, and the *p*-values are reported in the table below each plot.

Based on these similarity metrics, H₂ jobs exhibit a similar amount of skill, knowledge, and work activities overlap with OG jobs comparable to that of VRE jobs. However, a pairwise comparison is not reflective of how jobs will be distributed across occupations and how that may impact the relevance of skills and experience from the OG in these new jobs. To assess this, we pair the employment data from JEDI and IMPLAN with normalized O*NET data to compute a weighted average of skills, knowledge, and worker activities in the new jobs, and compare it with typical characteristics of OG workers in Texas. Figure 5 shows the differences in skill requirements, knowledge requirements, and work activities for these three sets of occupations. While O*NET collects data for dozens of skills, knowledge, and work activities, the data here is aggregated into broader categories for easy of viewing and to understand general trends (Supplemental Tables S6–S8). Here, we consider both the importance of a skill or activity, or its “level”, which is the reported level of complexity required for a job according to O*Net respondents. Regarding skills (Figs. 5a and 5b), VRE jobs emphasize systems-based skills (e.g., analysis and evaluation of socio-technical systems) and technical skills (e.g., installation and repair, operations analysis and control) much more than OG jobs. Conversely, H₂ occupations are more closely aligned with OG occupations, with all their skill requirements falling within 5% of the average importance for OG occupations. Furthermore, all skills categories have a similar or lower level of complexity needed for hydrogen occupations, suggesting that oil and gas workers likely already have the skills necessary to work in these occupations, whereas the systems and technical skills required for new VRE jobs involve a higher level of complexity than what they are currently expected to perform.

Significant gaps emerge between OG and VRE occupations when knowledge requirements are considered (Figs. 5c and 5d). Since a majority of new VRE occupations are wind and solar technicians and installers, the knowledge requirements are heavily skewed toward engineering and technology. While this is the most important knowledge requirement for OG jobs as well, VRE jobs also have a higher level of complexity. VRE occupations tend to also place more significance on soft skills and knowledge requirements, with education, management, and communication knowledge having 30–104% greater importance compared to OG occupations. In comparison, we observe that H₂ jobs have similar or lower importance and complexity requirements across most knowledge categories than OG occupations. The one exception is production-related knowledge (manufacturing and materials processing), which is considerably more important for H₂-related occupations. When we consider typical work activities, H₂ occupations place less importance on and require less capacity across all activity types than OG occupations. While this is largely true for VRE occupations as well, importance and complexity are both 10–20% higher manual and technical tasks that need to be performed as part of the job. Overall, worker requirements for H₂ jobs tend to be more closely aligned with those of existing OG jobs when we consider the distribution of jobs across industries and occupations. This suggests that H₂ occupations can help address the skill gap currently present between fossil-fuel and green jobs. However, H₂ jobs are still not perfectly aligned with OG jobs and have their own skill and knowledge gaps that need to be addressed, just not to the same degree as VRE occupations. Notably, this skill gap is only a reflection of the current workforce and does not account new jobs that may exist in the future. As

emerging technologies like electrolyzers develop, they will create new occupations not currently reflected in BLS or O*NET databases, similar to the emergence of new jobs for wind and solar as they gained prominence [28, 30, 60].

Figure 5: Comparison of the average normalized importance and level of complexity for various skills, knowledge requirements, and work activities for OG, VRE, and H2 occupations. Average values are calculated based on the weighted average of normalized O*NET data based on occupation output from IMPLAN and JEDI. The lines in each plot show the percent difference in

importance or level when comparing OG occupations to VRE occupations (purple), and OG occupations to H₂ occupations (yellow).

Figure 6 reflects the typical education, experience, and training requirements for OG, VRE, and H₂ occupations. More than 75% of OG workers considered in this analysis have, at most, a high school diploma, whereas both VRE and H₂ occupations typically require higher education. The majority (57%) of VRE occupations and 42% of H₂ occupations require some form of post-secondary education. So, while there is a lower educational barrier to transitioning to H₂ occupations, the requirements for some occupations will remain prohibitive for the vast majority of OG workers. Similarly, H₂ occupations tend to have lower requirements for relevant work experience. More than 40% of H₂ occupations require less than 1 year of prior work experience, and 78% require less than 4 years, whereas for VRE occupations, those values are 32% and 76%, respectively. Moreover, given the greater similarity discussed earlier, prior experience in OG occupations is more likely to be considered relevant to emerging H₂ jobs compared to VRE jobs. Lastly, training requirements for onboarding new workers are considerably lower for H₂ occupations, with 74% of jobs requiring less than a year of on-the-job training.

Figure 6: Percent breakdown of the (a) educational requirements, (b) relevant work experience, and (c) required on-the-job training for OG, VRE, and H₂ occupations. Percentages are calculated from weighted averages of occupational data derived from the IMPLAN and JEDI results.

In addition to location and skill differences, differences in job quality across OG, VRE, and H₂ occupations are also considered. While definitions of job quality vary and can be difficult to quantify, annual wages are a persistent and well-defined metric to indicate whether a job is considered good or decent by workers. OG occupations in this analysis have an average annual wage of \$79K, compared to \$51K for renewable occupations. While some VRE occupations offer comparable pay, the vast majority of new jobs are technicians and installers, which have

considerably lower pay than current extraction jobs, and which reduce the overall average wage for VRE workers, resulting in a 35% pay reduction on average for OG workers seeking to transition to these jobs. H₂ occupations earn higher overall salaries compared to VRE workers, with an average annual wage of \$65K. Thus, OG workers would only experience an 18% pay loss on average if they were to transition into an H₂ occupation. So, while OG workers would need to accept a pay reduction to transfer to either of these sectors, they would expect higher salaries if they were to transfer to H₂ jobs. However, while H₂ occupations have higher wages, their ability to support OG workers is limited due to how few H₂ jobs are generated in the results of this analysis. Figure 7 reflects the average annual wage of all (VRE+H₂) workers in each load zone across all scenarios. In cases where the majority of new jobs in a load zone are attributed to electrolyzers (e.g., the Far West load zone in the NZ-IT scenario), the salary reduction is smaller for OG workers; however, this pattern is not observed in most scenarios. In most cases, average wages in a load are similar to the average wage of \$51K for VRE occupations. Additionally, the cases with higher average wages still have a very small number of new jobs compared to the number of current OG workers in the same load zone. Thus, H₂ occupations might offer a very small subset of workers with a job similar to their current work in terms of skills and requirements, but still likely to pay less than their current job. This suggests that, although H₂ occupations could be of higher quality than VRE occupations, it remains insufficient to close the gap with existing OG occupations.

Figure 7: Average annual wages in each load zone across all scenarios. The “Current” column reflects wages for existing OG occupations included in this analysis, while all other columns only include new VRE and H₂ occupations. These results use 2023 wage data and do not assume any future wage growth.

This is not to say that jobs associated with H₂ production are inherently higher quality than those in VRE. In addition to discrepancies in annual wages, numerous other aspects of an occupation determine whether it can be considered high quality, such as concerns related to additional benefits (e.g., insurance, breaks, overtime pay), and job security [22]. There is evidence that these benefits are commonplace in wind and solar occupations, however there may be discrepancies amongst occupations within the sector, as these benefits are less common among non-White and non-English-speaking workers [64]. Moreover, non-economic factors related to the work itself may further indicate job quality. Such factors could include overall satisfaction, the level of work-related stress, the degree of autonomy and surveillance experienced by workers, and the skills workers are able to leverage while performing their tasks [21, 22]. As of now, it is unclear to what extent H₂ jobs can satisfy these additional criteria for job quality, as well as how much they will motivate OG workers to transition to this new sector, given the expected loss in pay. Future research is needed as new hydrogen infrastructure is deployed, and new jobs are created, to engage with workers, assess their experiences and the benefits they receive, and how those factors influence their perception of job quality.

Conclusion

Our findings provide insights into the workforce development potential of hydrogen electrolysis and the extent to which it can help support oil and gas workers in the energy transition. Using a set of coupled capacity-expansion and economic input-output models, we estimated the potential number of jobs generated by hydrogen production. Our results indicate that, while hydrogen electrolyzers have relatively low employment factors, on par with new wind capacity, they have strong secondary impacts on employment as the new wind and solar capacity required to power these electrolyzers also generate additional workforce opportunities. However, a regional analysis of these jobs reveals a significant spatial mismatch between existing oil and gas occupations and the new jobs generated by hydrogen production, further exacerbating the distributional gap observed in the literature on the energy transition and green jobs.

Compared with occupations associated with wind and solar, hydrogen occupations are much more closely aligned with current oil and gas jobs in terms of their skill and knowledge requirements and would, on average, have lower training requirements. While direct comparisons of individual oil and gas, renewable, and hydrogen occupations suggest a high level of overlap with oil and gas occupations, many of the expected job openings are in occupations that are less similar to oil and gas occupations, thereby limiting the transferability of skill and knowledge. This pattern is also evident in wages, with the majority of new renewable energy job openings in lower-paying occupations compared with oil and gas and hydrogen jobs. Nevertheless, workers transitioning to a new hydrogen job would still be likely to experience wage losses, and the number of hydrogen jobs are so few that their ability to offset worker losses is minimal.

Based on these results, early policy interventions are needed to effectively leverage the potential benefits of this emerging sector and support current oil and gas workers as the hydrogen supply chain develops. Programs need to be established to identify and place prospective workers and to mitigate hiring bottlenecks as opportunities arise, particularly when oil and gas employees may be reluctant to transfer. Moreover, since the number of jobs created by electrolysis is so low relative

to renewable energy jobs, recruitment efforts should prioritize specific groups or occupations that will likely have the greatest barriers to transitioning to other green jobs. Workforce development programs (e.g., on-site trainings, certifications, internships) should prioritize gaps in prospective workers' skill sets to minimize transition time. Efforts to transition oil and gas workers into hydrogen programs should then emphasize education and skill building related to manufacturing and process skills. The more severe knowledge gaps in renewable energy jobs, meanwhile, suggest that longer programs may be necessary to effectively transition oil and gas workers and prioritize entirely different skill sets. Any local, state, or federal programs to facilitate these transitions should be developed in consultation with labor organizations. Unions and other organizations can more concretely identify issues experienced by workers they represent, how to best support them in a transition, and avoid exacerbating potential inequities currently present in various industries. To this end, further efforts are needed to increase union participation in these emerging sectors.

While this study performs a regional analysis to provide a more granular representation of the locational impacts of new technologies compared to state- or national-level studies, highly localized assessments coupled with community engagement are needed to fully understand the impacts of shifts in technologies and energy production on individual communities. Furthermore, the skills and wage analyses of this study rely on occupation data from the current workforce and do not reflect emerging occupations. As new jobs become more prominent in the workforce and new data becomes available, additional efforts can clarify the extent to which potential new jobs could address current workforce gaps in the energy transition. Nevertheless, the findings of this work are critical to provide early insights into the potential benefits and impacts of the hydrogen supply chain and can be leveraged to support oil and gas workers through the ongoing energy transition.

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